

Analysis of Student Learning Independence in State Junior High School 14 Semarang

Arie Wahyuni^{1*}, Destia Wahyu Hidayati²

Universitas Ivet

Corresponding Author: Arie Wahyuni ariewahyuni20@gmail.com

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords: Analysis, Student Learning Independence, State Junior High School

Received : 22, October

Revised : 21, November

Accepted: 30, December

©2023 Wahyuni, Hidayati: This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).

ABSTRACT

Student independence in learning must be grown, so that they can develop their creative ideas without the full support of the teacher. Learning independence is largely determined by applicable learning media and models. Therefore, it is necessary to analyze the independence of learning. Students as a basis for consideration of the use of a particular learning model or environment. The implementation of this research was at SMP Negeri 14 Semarang. The data analysis technique used is simple descriptive statistics and qualitative analysis. Mass Research Recommendations to be able to do this in the future, a learning model is needed that incorporates elements of technology to increase student learning independence through student activation learning models in schools.

INTRODUCTION

Studying at school requires students to make exceptions have technical skills, but also have a broad outlook, attitude of mind and a certain personality. Because achieving this competency, only certain models, students learn at different levels of education in schools. Learning to be yourself is emphasized by students. However, there is a relatively low level of learning culture in schools, as shown by the results of previous studies. Many students read books only to complete assignments given by lecturers (Taufiq, 2018). Students do not have direct self-learning initiative if the teacher does not at this time; seldom read school materials; questions are still very low; Copying work results from friends where references can be obtained via the internet (Arliani & Widjajanti, 2006). The most important reason for students failing in studies is the lack of self-regulation (Cubukcu, 2009). Lack of independent students can learn to lead to negative behavior. This is less creative and confident students think because while this is learning that is done, for example acting when the teacher receives a stimulus such as the concept of behavior emphasizing stimulus and response.

Learning objectives are expected from students to be lifelong learners, independent learners are independent learning attitudes that can acquire, store and process their own knowledge (Jade, 2015). A lifelong learner is to equip students with basic life skills (Jade, 2015). It is no longer intelligence that is an important factor determining success, but the way students learn with the right strategies to manage motivation, behavior and learning is one thing that determines (Jade, 2015). This problem with the concept of independence learning independence emphasizes autonomy and control accompanying individuals to monitor and manage learning to achieve goals and competencies owned by (Nyandowe & Zubair, 2017; Hah & Reigeluth, 2017; Pint Kaya, 2000). Effective learners are able to self-regulate analyze tasks, set productive goals and choose strategies to achieve their goals.

For this in the learning process, students must actively ask questions, write notes and plan to achieve the desired learning goals (Paris & Paris, 2001). Independent learning involves several components, namely cognitive (TEAL, 2010; Panadero, 2017), metacognitive (TEAL, 2010; Tzoharrozen & Kramarski, 2014; Williamson, 2015; Baker, 2017), motivation (TEAL, 2010; Tzohar-rozen & Kramarski, 2014; Williamson, 2015; Panadero, 2017), behavior (Williamson, 2015; Panadero, 2017) and affective/emotional reflection on learning (Tzoharrozen & Kramarski, 2014; Panadero, 2017). So, on that basis learning independence is connected with the five existing components. Learning independence is the ability of students to carry out learning activities based on performance, responsibility and motivation of students (Russia, 2014) and Majid (2013) states that independent learning is a learning strategy whose goal is to build individuality, independence and development initiatives. Each student can choose one that determines their own learning material and progress in this study.

LITERATURE REVIEW

According to research by Hidayati & Listiyan (2013), there are six indicators of learning independence. These indicators are; (1) independence from other people; (2) you have faith; (3) disciplinary behavior; (4) you have responsibilities; (5) act on their own initiative; and (6) self-regulating.

Table 1. Learning Independence Indicator

No	Indicator	Sub-Indicators
1	Responsibility in learning	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Have a sense of responsibility. 2. Self-evaluate. 3. Learning facilities and furniture. 4. Independence from others.
2	Goals in learning	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Setting learning goals and planning. 2. Self-consequences.
3	Discipline in learning	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Behave discipline. 2. Set study time. 3. Have confidence.
4	Continuity in learning	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Repeating study material. 2. Make a summary of the lessons that have been given. 3. Check the records.
5	Activeness in learning	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Behave based on self-initiative. 2. Read books, look for other sources of information.
6	Self-control in learning	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Set and change the desire in learning. 2. Self-control.

Harvest shows that learning is self-sufficient does not mean self-study (Russia, 2014). The most important thing in independent learning is increasing the capacity and ability of students to learn without outside help, etc. After all, students are not addicts to their teachers, mentors, friends or other people for learning. In independent studies, students themselves try it first. First, understand the content of the lesson. If you have a problem, students will ask or discuss the teacher, mentor, friend or other person. Independent students can find the learning resources they need. The teacher's work is in progress. Independent learning becomes a moderator, who must be prepared to provide

assistance to students when needed (Russia, 2014). a friend as important as possible a partner in mutual learning debate.

Based on expert opinion, from this it can be concluded that learning independence is a skill with the desire of students to manage their own learning activities responsibly without having to depend on others. Self-study is a method. Learn where you can or can't succeed I decide for myself. Much of the previous research on this topic of self-directed learning targeted to conceptualize and view emotions. Student feelings that change from time to time acquire learning assignments (Ben-Eliyahu & Linnenbrink-Garcia, 2013; baker, 2017), self-learning in metal knowledge (Cubukcu, 2009; Panadero, 2017); language checking (Nejuangi, 2015); seen independent learning cognitive, behavioral and motivational aspects (Baker, 2017). Because this study examines the profile of student learning independence at the university. Moreover, the research question is as independent learning during the time that is owned by students. The purpose of this study was to analyze students' initial attitudes towards independent learning.

METHODOLOGY

This study uses data in the form of numbers obtained from the results of self-study surveys of SMP Negeri 14 Semarang students. This study uses a quantitative approach so that certain populations or samples are used accordingly. According to Sugiyono (2015) which is claimed by this study to be a quantitative study of a particular population or sample, the sampling technique is usually random sampling, data collection using research tools, data analysis in statistical form.

This study tries to create ideas about independent learning in global schools as a whole, especially in SMP Negeri 14 Semarang. This lesson describes independent learning after a few examples, students have good, moderate and not so good learning autonomy. The population in this study is students of SMP Negeri 14 Semarang who take part in this special global perspective with a number of up to 422 students. A data collection instrument with a list of questionnaire questions was used to collect data about the independence profile of social studies. The answer choices used in this instrument are always (SL), often (SR), rarely (J) and never (TP).

RESULT AND DISSCUSION

The respondents of this study were prospective students of SMP Negeri 14 Semarang with a total of 81 students. The results of this study resulted in 75% of students usually having good self-confidence, 60% of students having good discipline, 55% of students having good initiative and 60% of students having very good responsibility.

Prospective junior high school students show all indicators of independent learning, namely self-confidence, discipline, initiative and responsibility to show something good. The research scores are consistent. Dina & Nugrahen's (2017) statement which shows the level of student learning autonomy is localized in good classes, even with different percentages. This score is the lowest indicator of initiative compared to other indicators, the same

as Hariyanto, Murtinugraha, Iriani's research (2012) showing a lack of student initiative if students have limited teaching materials, usually do not take advantage of what opportunities exist in the library, it is very important to study independently, it is recommended to stay at home and only rely on the material provided by the teacher.

Initiative, self-confidence and responsibility can be increased by the Isroah movement and Sumarsih (2013) found that there must be a problem encouraging students to think. In this case, the teacher must give students a lot of freedom to research, explore, learn and solve problems on their own. After students get used to learning and solving problems on their own, hopefully a big responsibility for what they do and what they do creates increased trust (Isroah & Sumarsih, 2013).

The causal factors are in accordance with the existence of independent learning. According to Shah (2011), the author also includes internal, external and access factors studying internal factors including physical factors (including physical fitness) and mental factors. External factors include the social environment (eg teachers, classmates, etc.) and non-social (eg appearance). Classrooms, school locations, weather, etc.), and the last is a factor or learning requirement which can now be called a curriculum. Learning independence can be recognized as learning based on self-initiation. In the opinion of Ranti, Budiarti, Trisna (2017) learning independence is a requirement for independent learning, not depending on other people who also have a will, responsibility for oneself, solving learning problems. Learning independence becomes a reality when students actively manage themselves, everything they do taxes and so on to plan something deeper in the lessons learned and students also want to actively learn.

The results of this study are consistent with Gilmore's theory (1974) which states that independence must be supported and carried out with strong confidence because without all actions and decisions made without hesitation. Gilmore (1974) found that this independence is an important part of personality achieved in individuals facing challenges and achieving something indicating success in life free expression, responsibility, thinking about things, feeling secure when different from others and creativity. This is in accordance with Rogers (in Koswara, 1991) for independent people there are things that have problems without the help of others. He tries hard to overcome the problems in his life.

Self-learning people have characteristic qualities such as freedom to think confidently, responsibility to judge in difficulties or make decisions, feeling safe at times different from others, initiative and a creative base, and aspiring the ability to survive problems without other people's help. As expected what students can and do maturity through self-learning with confidence, responsibility reactions and the ability to deal with life, can find their skills in this area of academic and problem-solving life without the problems and problems of other assistance, influence and control.

CONCLUSSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Therefore, it is necessary to analyze the independence of learning. Students as a basis for consideration of the use of a particular learning model or environment. The implementation of this research was at SMP Negeri 14 Semarang. The data analysis technique used is simple descriptive statistics and qualitative analysis. Mass Research Recommendations to be able to do this in the future, a learning model is needed that incorporates elements of technology to increase student learning independence through student activation learning models in schools.

FURTHER RESEARCH

This research still has limitations so further research needs to be done on this topic "Analysis of Student Learning Independence in State Junior High School 14 Semarang".

REFERENCES

- Arliani, E., & Widjajanti, D. B. (2006). Upaya Peningkatan Kemandirian Belajar Mahasiswa Program Studi Pendidikan Matematika Melalui Pendekatan Kontrak Perkuliahan (Learning Contract) dalam Pembelajaran Mata Kuliah Rancangan Percobaan. In Seminar Nasional MIPA 2006 dengan Tema Penelitian, Pendidikan, dan Penerapan MIPA serta Peranannya dalam Peningkatan Keprofesionalan Pendidik dan Tenaga Kependidikan (pp. 103-112).
- Cubukcu, F. (2009). Learner autonomy, self-regulation and metacognition. *International Electronic Journal of Elementary Education*, 2(1), 53-64.
- Dina & Nugraheni, A.R.E. (2017). Profil kemandirian dan minat belajar mahasiswa pendidikan kimia pada mata kuliah wawasan dan kajian MIPA melalui pembelajaran elearning. *Jurnal Inovasi Pendidikan Kimia*, 11(2), 1921-1931.
- Gilmore, J.V. (1974). *The productive personality*. San Fransisco. Allian Publishing Company
- Hariyanto, D., Murtinugraha, R.E., & Iriani, T. (2012). Hubungan kemandirian belajar terhadap hasil belajar mekanika teknik II pada mahasiswa program studi Pendidikan Teknik Bangunan Universitas Negeri Jakarta. *Jurnal PenSil Jurusan Teknik Sipil FT UNJ*, I (1), 21-40.
- Huh, Y., & Reigeluth, C. M. (2017). Self-Regulated Learning: The Conceptual Framework and a Vision of New Paradigm, Technology System, and Pedagogical Support. *Journal of Educational Technology Systems*, 46(2), 191-214.
- Isroah, & Sumarsih. (2013). Analisis kemandirian belajar mahasiswa program studi Pendidikan akuntansi. *Fakultas Ilmu Sosial dan Ekonomi:*

Universitas Negeri Yogyakarta. Jurnal Pendidikan Akuntansi Indonesia, XI (1), 1-12

- Jado, S. M. A. (2015). The Effect of using Learning Journals on Developing Self-Regulated Learning and Reflective Thinking among Pre-Service Teachers in Jordan. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 6(5), 89-104.
- Koswara, E. (1991). *Teori-teori kepribadian*. Bandung: PT Eresco
- Majid, A. (2013). *Strategi pembelajaran*. Bandung: PT Remaja Rosdakarya.
- Nejabati, N. (2015). The Effects of Teaching Self-regulated Learning Strategies on EFL Students Reading Comprehension. *Journal of Language Teaching and Research*, 6(6), 1343-1348.
- Noor, J. DR. (2012). *Metodologi penelitian*. Jakarta. Kencana Prenada Media Group.
- Nyandowe, M., & Zubair, O. (2017). Self-regulated learning: why is it important compared to traditional learning in medical education? *Advances in Medical Education and Practice*, 8, 243-246.
- Panadero, E. (2017). A Review of Selfregulated Learning: Six and Four Directions for Research. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 8(April), 1-28.
- Paris, S. G., & Paris, A. H. (2001). Classroom Applications of Research on Self-Regulated Learning. *Educational Psychologist*, 36(2), 89-101.
- Pintrich, P. R. (2000). Handbook of SelfRegulation 4 5'l. In *Handbook of Self-Regulation* (pp. 451-502).
- Ranti, M.G., Budiarti, I., & Trisna, B.N. (2017). Pengaruh kemandirian belajar (self-regulated learning) terhadap hasil belajar mahasiswa pada mata kuliah Struktur Aljabar. *Math Didactic: Jurnal Pendidikan Matematika*, 3(1), Januari - April 2017.
- Rusman. (2014). *Model-model pembelajaran mengembangkan profesionalisme guru*. Jakarta: Raja Grafindo persada.
- Sanjayanti, A., Sulistiono, & Budiretnani, D. A. (2015). Tingkat kemandirian belajar siswa SMAN 1 Kediri Kelas XI MIA-5 pada model PBL materi system reproduksi manusia. *Seminar Nasional XII Pendidikan Biologi FKIP UNS*, 12, 361-363.
- Sudijono, A. (2009). *Pengantar statistic pendidikan*. Jakarta: PT. Raja Grafindo Persada.

- Sugiyono. (2015). *Metode penelitian kombinasi (Mix Methods)*. Bandung: Alfabeta.
- Syah, M. (2011). *Psikologi belajar*. Jakarta: PT Raja Grafindo Persada
- Taufiq, A. (2018). Paradigma Baru Pendidikan Tinggi dan Makna Kuliah Bagi Mahasiswa. *MADANI Jurnal Politik Dan Sosial Kemasyarakatan*, 10(1), 34-52.
- TEAL. (2010). *Self-Regulated Learning American Institute for Research*.
- Tzohar-rozen, M., & Kramarski, B.-I. (2014). Metacognition, Motivation, and Emotions: Contribution of Self-Regulated Learning to Solving Mathematical Problems. *Global Education Review*, 1(4), 76-95.
- Williamson, G. (2015). Self-regulated Learning: an Overview of Metacognition, Motivation and Behaviour. *Journal of Initial Teacher Inquiry*, 1, 25-27.
- Winartiningsih, W.E., Halimah, S., & Mahmu`ddin. (2018). Analisis kemandirian belajar pada mata pelajaran IPS siswa kelas VIII MTSN 1 KOTIM. *EQUILIBRIA PENDIDIKAN: Jurnal Ilmiah Pendidikan Ekonomi*, 3(1), 28-35.